

A STUDY ON HUMAN RESOURCE DEVELOPMENT CLIMATE AND ITS IMPACT ON JOB SATISFACTION IN PUBLIC SECTOR UNDERTAKINGS

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Abstract:

The objective of this paper is to examine the nature of the HRD Climate and the impact of developmental climate on job satisfaction of the employees working in the PSUs. The founding fathers of the republic used the public undertaking as an essential and vibrant element in the building-up of India's economy. One of the basic objectives of starting the public undertaking in India was to build infrastructure for economic development and rapid economic growth. The data was collected from employees of four major public sector undertakings, i.e. Central Warehousing Corporation, MMTC Ltd., Bharat Heavy Electricals Ltd. and National Buildings Construction Corporation. The results of the study offered realistic support for the existence of a positive relationship and statistically significant impact of HRD Climate and its various components, i.e., General Climate, HRD Mechanisms and OCTAPACE Culture, on employees' job satisfaction in the companies.

Keywords: HRD Climate, Job Satisfaction, Public Sector Undertakings, General Climate, OCTAPACE Culture

INTRODUCTION:

Public sector undertakings (PSUs) are companies established by the central government under the Companies Act or as statutory corporations under specific statutes of parliament. PSUs were established in the early 1950s for rapid industrial and economic growth, to create necessary infrastructure, for employment generations, to promote balanced regional development and to assist the growth of other industries. The founding fathers of our republic used the public undertaking as an essential and vibrant element in the building-up of India's economy. One of the basic objectives of starting the public undertaking in India was to build infrastructure for economic development and rapid economic growth.

Since their inception, public enterprises have played an important role in achieving the objective of economic growth with social justice. In 1950s 58 industries were reserved for the public sector undertakings, which was brought down to 18 in 1991 and now it is 4. There are 35 PSUs in the BSE-200 index accounting for almost two-fifth of market capitalization, with an aggregate market capitalization of Rs. 3,84,600 crore.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Many researches have been conducted on HRD climate. The result has shown that HRD climate affects the performance of the employees. Richa Chaudhary, Santosh Rangnekar, Mukesh Kumar Barua (2012) determined the level of HRD climate and the perceptions of HRD climate which differ for different nature of organizations, at different hierarchical levels, for different age groups, by gender. Dr. Birajit Mohanty, Ms. Susmitaparija, Mr. Ghansyamsahu (2012) analysed the impact of HRD climate on job performance of the employee. Parikshit Joshi,

Gurjeet Kaur / A Study on Human Resource Development Climate and its Impact on Job Satisfaction in Public Sector Undertakings

Anuj Srivastava (2012) examined the nature of HRD Climate prevailing in Indian PSU's and determined problematic areas.

N. Sekar, Krishnaveni Muttiah, B. R. Santosh (2012) explored the nature of HRD climate prevalent in manufacturing organizations and the extent to which workers needs are satisfied through their roles to suggest areas for improvement based on the perception of workers. Prof. I.K. Kilam, Neeraj (2012) attempted to understand the HR climate in banks and the experience of a target group of executives in various public sector banks in India with respect to their career in the bank.

HYPOTHESES

- There is a significant relationship between HRD Climate and the level of job satisfaction of the employees.
- General Climate has a significant impact on the level of job satisfaction of the employees of PSUs.
- HRD Mechanism has a significant impact on the level job satisfaction of the employees of PSUs.
- OCTAPACE culture has a significant impact on the level of job satisfaction of employees PSUs.
- Total HRD Climate has a significant impact on the level of job satisfaction of the employees of PSUs.

METHODOLOGY

The data was collected from both primary and secondary sources to conduct the study. Primary sources includes **The HRD Climate Survey** developed by Rao and Abraham (1990) at Centre for HRD Xavier Labour Relations Institute (XLRI, India) to survey the extent to which a development climate exist in organizations, was used. This instrument consists of 38 questions on a 5 point scale ranging from 5 (Always almost true) to 1 (Not at all true) to measure the elements of HRD Climate which can be grouped into 3 broad categories referred to earlier, i.e. General Climate, OCTAPACE Culture, and HRD Mechanisms. Out of 38 statements 25 statements was used for the study.

Job Satisfaction Scale developed by C.N. Daftuar consisting of 19 items including 2 which measure separately overall satisfaction with the companies and overall satisfaction with the work was used for the purpose. The respondents were asked to rate each statement on a five point scale ranging from 5 (strongly agree) to 1 (strongly disagree).10 statements was used for the study.

Secondary data was collected for this study through various sources, i.e. internet, journals and books. 100 employees across all divisions in the four companies in Delhi were the sample size. Random sampling was the method adopted for the selection of sample. To analyze the result, statistical measures such as Mean, Standard Deviation were used. Correlation analysis was applied to study the relationship between HRD climate and job satisfaction. Linear regression was applied to analyses the impact of HRD climate and its various components on level of job satisfaction of employees of PSUs.

FINDINGS

In order to determine HRD Climate among employees in four public sector undertakings, mean analysis was conducted for the individual variables. Table 1 showed the results of descriptive statistics of General Climate. The result indicated that the seniors guide their juniors and prepare them for future responsibilities/ roles they are likely to take up. The top management also believes that human resources are an extremely important resource and that they have to be treated more humanly. Moreover, managers in these organizations believe that employee behavior can be changed and people can be developed at any stage of their life and employees in these organizations are also helpful to each other.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics of General Climate

Statements	N	Mean	Standard Deviation
1) The top management believes that human resources are an extremely important resource and that they have to be treated more humanly.	100	4.05	.770
2) Development of the subordinates is seen as an important part of their job by the managers / officers here.	100	3.88	1.104
3) The personnel policies in this organization facilitate employee development.	100	3.51	.522
4) The top management is willing to invest a considerable part of their time and other resources to ensure the development of employees.	100	3.96	1.044
5) Managers in this organization believe that employee behaviour can be changed and people can be developed at any stage of their life.	100	4.02	1.101
6) People in this organization are helpful to each other.	100	4.02	1.092
7) Employees in this organization are very informal and do not hesitate to discuss their personal problems with their supervisors.	100	3.53	.594
8) Seniors guide their juniors and prepare them for future responsibilities/ roles they are likely to take up.	100	4.23	.723
9) The top management of this organization makes efforts to identify and utilize the potential of the employees.	100	4.01	1.020
Overall GC		35.21	6.629

Table 2 showed the results of descriptive statistics of HRD Mechanism. Result indicated that employees are sponsored for training programmes on the basis of genuine training needs and employees returning from training programmes are given opportunities to try out what they have learnt. It also indicated that employees in these organizations take pains to find out their strengths and weaknesses from their supervising officers or colleagues and weaknesses of employees are communicated to them in a non-threatening way. This shows that companies are having a reasonable level of development orientation and employees are contended with the same.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics of HRD Mechanism

Statements	N	Mean	Standard Deviation
10) Promotion decisions are based on the suitability of the promotee rather than on favouritism.	100	3.58	.554
11) An employee is appreciated by his supervisors when he does good work.	100	3.49	.674
12) Employees are encouraged to experiment with and try out new methods and try out creative ideas.	100	3.92	.939
13) When any employee makes a mistake his supervisors treat it with understanding and help him to learn from such mistakes rather than punishing him or discouraging him.	100	3.46	.593
14) Weaknesses of employees are communicated to them in a non-threatening way.	100	4.12	.844
15) Employees in this organization take pains to find out their strengths and weaknesses from their supervising officers or colleagues.	100	4.23	.763

Gurjeet Kaur / A Study on Human Resource Development Climate and its Impact on Job Satisfaction in Public Sector Undertakings

16) When employees are sponsored for training, they take it seriously and try to learn from the programmes they attend.	100	4.05	.770
18) Employees are sponsored for training programmes on the basis of genuine training needs.	100	4.29	.715
24) Job-rotation in this organization facilitates employee development.	100	3.95	.845
Overall HRD Mechanism		39.32	5.414

Table 3 showed the results of descriptive statistics of OCTAPACE Culture. The result indicated that delegation of authority is there to encourage juniors to develop handling higher responsibilities is quite common in these organizations. Employees are also encouraged to take initiative and do things on their own without having to wait for instructions from supervisor and team spirit is of high order in these organizations.

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics of OCTAPACE Culture

Statements	N	Mean	Standard Deviation
19) Employees are encouraged to take initiative and do things on their own without having to wait for instructions from supervisors.	100	4.23	.897
20) Delegation of authority to encourage juniors to develop handling higher responsibilities is quite common in this organization.	100	4.25	.892
21) When seniors delegate authority to juniors, the juniors use it as an opportunity for development.	100	4.03	.846
22) Team spirit is of high order in this organization.	100	4.13	.950
23) When problems arise people discuss these problems openly and try to solve them rather than keep accusing each other behind the back.	100	3.92	.837
Overall OCTOPACE Culture		20.56	3.430

Table 4 showed the descriptive analysis of overall HRD Climate. Examining the three major components of HRD Climate i.e. General Climate, OCTAPACE Culture and HRD Mechanisms, the results indicated HRD Mechanics influences the Overall HRD Climate more as compared to rest of the components.

Table 4: Descriptive Statistics of Overall HRD Climate

	N	Mean	Standard Deviation
General Climate	100	35.21	6.629
HRD Mechanics	100	39.32	5.414
OCTOPACE Culture	100	20.56	3.430
HRD Climate	100	95.09	14.768

Mean analysis was also conducted to study the level of Job Satisfaction among the employees in four public sector undertakings. Table 5 showed the results of descriptive statistics of Job Satisfaction. The result indicated that the employees are highly satisfied with the number of opportunities that are provided to do something that makes use of their abilities as well as with the way the co-workers get along with each other. They are also contented with the

fact that their work is suitably recognized in the organization. On the whole, the results showed that people are happy with the work and the organization in general.

Table 5: Descriptive Statistics of Job Satisfaction

Statements	N	Mean	Standard Deviation
25) My job provides adequate opportunities to do different things from time to time.	100	3.77	.952
26) My job provides adequate opportunities to do different things from time to time.	100	3.98	.816
27) My job provides adequate opportunities to do something that makes use of my abilities.	100	4.23	.750
28) My job provides adequate opportunities for advancement on this job.	100	3.37	.661
29) I'm happy with the working conditions.	100	3.51	.798
30) I'm happy with the way my co-workers get along with each other.	100	4.20	.651
31) My job provides me a feeling of accomplishment.	100	3.39	.737
32) There are adequate opportunities for future growth (in efficiency).	100	3.46	.809
33) Social conditions are appropriate for the job within the organization.	100	4.13	.950
34) My work is suitably recognized in the organization.	100	3.92	.837
Overall JS		37.96	5.538

In order to test the first hypotheses, i.e., whether there is a significant relationship between HRD Climate and the level of job satisfaction of the employees of PSUs, Pearson correlation was used. The result indicated in Table 6 showed that significant positive correlation of 0.901 exists between HRD Climate and Job Satisfaction. This proves that HRD Climate is a contributing or influencing factor to increase the level of job satisfaction of employees.

Table 6: Correlation between Job Satisfaction and HRD Climate

		Job satisfaction	HRD climate
Pearson Correlation	Job satisfaction	1.000	.901
	HRD climate	.901	1.000
Sig. (1-tailed)	Job satisfaction	.	.000
	HRD climate	.000	.
N	Job satisfaction	100	100
	HRD climate	100	100

Regression analysis was performed to explain the second hypotheses, i.e., there is a significant impact of General climate on the level of job satisfaction of the employees of PSUs. The result indicated in Table 7 showed the amount of association, i.e., the F-Value of 224.816 which is significant at 5% level of significance proves that the regression model is valid. The result of the study also indicated that General Climate has a positive impact on job satisfaction as it explained as 69.6 per cent of total variance. Thus, it can be said that job satisfaction of employees of PSUs is significantly influenced by General Climate.

Gurjeet Kaur / A Study on Human Resource Development Climate and its Impact on Job Satisfaction in Public Sector Undertakings

Table 7: Result of Regression Model of General Climate on Job Satisfaction

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.835 ^a	.696	.693	3.067	.696	224.816	1	98	.000

a. Predictors: (Constant), General Climate

In-order to test the third hypotheses, i.e., there is a significant impact of HRD Mechanism on the level of job satisfaction of employees of PSUs, regression analysis was performed. Table 8 presented the result that the amount of association, i.e., the F-Value of 342.661 which is significant at 5% level of significance. The result of the study also indicated that HRD Mechanism has a significant impact on the job satisfaction as it explained as 72.6 per cent of total variance. Thus, it can be said that job satisfaction is significantly influenced by HRD Mechanism.

Table 8: Result of Regression Model of HRD Mechanism on Job Satisfaction

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.882 ^a	.778	.775	2.625	.778	342.661	1	98	.000

a. Predictors: (Constant), HRD Mechanics

In-order to test the fourth hypotheses, i.e., there is a significant impact of OCTOPACE culture on level of job satisfaction of the employees of PSUs, regression analysis was performed. The result in Table 9 showed the amount of association, i.e., the F-Value of 316.754 which is significant at 5% level of significance. The result of the study also indicated that OCTOPACE Culture has a significant impact on the job satisfaction as it explained as 76.4 per cent of total variance. Thus, it can be said that job satisfaction is significantly influenced by OCTOPACE Culture.

Table 9: Result of Regression Model of OCTOPACE Culture on Job Satisfaction

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.874 ^a	.764	.761	2.705	.764	316.754	1	98	.000

a. Predictors: (Constant), OCTOPACE Culture

In-order to test the fifth hypotheses, i.e., there is a significant impact of total HRD Climate on level of job satisfaction of the employees of PSUs, regression analysis was performed. The result in Table 10 showed the amount of association, i.e., the F-Value of 422.06 which is significant at 5% level of significance. The result of the study also indicated that total HRD Climate has a significant impact on the job satisfaction as it explained as 81.2 per cent of total variance. Thus, it can be said that job satisfaction is significantly influenced by total HRD Climate of the organization.

Table 10: Result of Regression Model of HRD Climate on Job Satisfaction

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.901 ^a	.812	.810	2.416	.812	422.056	1	98	.000

a. Predictors: (Constant), HRD climate

CONCLUSION

Every business organization is attaching immense value to human resource because human resources are the biggest source of competitive advantage and have the capability of converting all the other resources in to valuable product/service. The effective performance of the human resource depends on the type of HRD climate that prevails in an organization, if it is good than the employee's performance will be high, but if it is average or poor, then the performance of the employees will be low. Therefore, the study of HRD climate and its components is very important for every organization. The results of the study have shown that the independent variable, i.e., HRD Climate and its components (i.e., General Climate, HRD

Mechanism and OCTAPACE Culture) have a direct and positive impact on the dependent variable, i.e., job satisfaction which meant that the improvement of one independent variable caused the improvement in the level of job satisfaction.

It was concluded that there is a significant relationship between job satisfaction and HRD climate and its three components. Any positive change in HRD Climate and its components in the organization will bring about positive changes in level of job satisfaction of the employees of the organizations.

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